

Faculdade Católica Paulista

Food Engineering Course — Multidisciplinary Extension 8

**PASTEURIZATION IN FOCUS:
Calculating the Energy for Food Safety**

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Abstract

This technical work addresses the thermodynamic sizing and feasibility assessment of a continuous pasteurization system for a new dairy product, integrating concepts of mass, volume and sensible heat balance. The objective was to calculate the thermal demand required to heat 4m³/h of fluid from 18 °C to 75 °C and to assess the sufficiency of a 30 kW industrial heater over a residence time of 60 minutes. Methodologically, the fundamental equations of calorimetry and mass conservation were applied based on thermophysical data of the fluid. The results indicated a mass flow rate of 4120 kg/h and a thermal demand of 939,360 kJ/h. The comparison of the data revealed that the available heater supplies only 108,000 kJ within the stipulated time, operating with an efficiency of only 11.5 %. Given the insufficiency of the equipment and the imminent microbiological risk from under-pasteurization, it is concluded that the improvement and safety of the process depend on replacing the current infrastructure with a heat exchanger of optimal power of 300 kW.

Keywords: Pasteurization. Energy Balance. Heat Exchange. Food Engineering. Optimal Power.

1. Introduction

According to Normative Instruction No. 76 of November 26, 2018, of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply (MAPA), the technical regulation on the identity and quality of refrigerated raw milk and pasteurized milk is established (MAPA, 2018).

Milk, being a product of high nutritional value, in addition to the sensory characteristics essential to the consumer such as odor, color and texture, makes ensuring microbiological safety and the correct use of processing technologies fundamental. To meet the demand of consumers who require innovation such as *clean label*, the adaptation must also ensure the shelf-life (*Shelf-life*) of the products. To this end, the continuous optimization and improvement of processes become golden directions for the milk processing chain (Brito, 2019).

Among the processes, special emphasis is given to heat treatment of the pasteurization type which, according to Embrapa (2021), consists of eliminating pathogens and reducing the total microbial load. Compared to sterilization, it does not completely eliminate the microbiota, only the main agents that cause diseases in humans, whether through direct ingestion or exposure to the toxins present. For there to be a balance between the efficiency of the heat treatment (microbiological safety) without compromising the nutritional and sensory qualities, it is essential to carry out a correct thermodynamic sizing of the process (Cavero G., 2013).

Therefore, this work aims to perform the mass and energy balance for an industrial heater (heat exchanger) project for milk, verifying the technical feasibility of a continuous pasteurization operation.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Fundamentals of Thermodynamics in Thermal Processes

For the fluid to reach the safety temperature without nutritional degradation or energy waste, the correct formulation of the mass and energy balance of the system is indispensable.

2.1.1 Mass balance in steady state

In continuous industrial systems the processes operate, for the most part, in steady state (stationary); this means that the properties, such as total mass, occupied volume and mass flow rate of the system, remain constant over time.

Once the permanence of the properties is established, the principle of mass conservation (originally by Lomonosov, popularly disseminated by Lavoisier) determines that, in a closed system, mass can neither be created nor destroyed. Applying this concept to fluids, the mass flow that enters the system must be exactly equal to what leaves it. (Modern Physics, 2024)

When dealing with a heat exchange system, it is necessary to consider the density of the fluid since it is directly influenced by temperature and acts as a factor that indicates the real amount of matter under flow. The specific density of a fluid (ρ) can be expressed by:

$$\rho = m/V \quad (1)$$

where, ρ is the specific density of the fluid, m is the mass and V is the volume (which, in this case, flow rate will be used). The mass flow rate (\dot{m}), in turn, is expressed by:

$$\dot{m} = m/t \quad (2)$$

where, \dot{m} is the total mass flow rate, m is the mass and t is time. Isolating the term m in equation (1) and substituting it into (2), we obtain:

$$\dot{m} = (\rho \cdot V)/t \quad (3)$$

The volumetric flow rate (Q) is defined by the equation:

$$Q = V/t \quad (4)$$

where, Q is volumetric flow rate, V is volume and t is time. Substituting the volumetric flow rate (4) into equation 3, the final expression for mass flow becomes:

$$\dot{m} = \rho \cdot Q \quad (5)$$

2.1.2 Energy balance of sensible heat

To determine the thermal demand of the heat exchanger, one must start from the First Law of Thermodynamics, which indicates the principle of energy conservation. As previously established, the studied system is stationary, and therefore its kinetic and potential energy variations are negligible. Considering that the only form of heat transfer to the fluid originates from the heat exchanger, the heat transfer rate of the equipment must be equal to the enthalpy variation of the fluid.

Since in this model it is only a matter of temperature variation without a change of physical state, the energy in transition is classified as sensible heat. The amount of heat required for the fluid to reach the ideal processing temperature derives from the fundamental equation of calorimetry:

$$Q = m \cdot c \cdot \Delta T \quad (6)$$

where, m is the mass flow rate of the fluid, c is the specific heat of the fluid (a particular property of each material that represents the capacity to store thermal energy per unit of mass for each degree of variation of its temperature) and ΔT is the thermal variation of the operation, given the difference between the final temperature and initial temperature.

2.2 Thermal capacity and heat exchanger efficiency

The feasibility of a continuous operation that involves a change in temperature is governed by the laws of heat transfer. A process in which heat flows from a higher-temperature region

to another lower one through direct contact is called conduction. This phenomenon represents the spontaneous search for thermal equilibrium, as substantiated by the Second Law of Thermodynamics. (Barrosa, 2004).

In industrial practice, the rate of heat required by the fluid is evaluated, that is, how much heat is necessary for it to reach a specific temperature, and what is the maximum rate of energy that the equipment can transfer in a given time interval.

If the power of the heat exchanger is lower than the operational demand, that is, if it is undersized, the fluid will not reach the ideal temperature within the determined residence time. If the milk does not reach the pasteurization temperature, there will be a serious operational, technological and, above all, microbiological compromise.

3. Methodological Procedures

The methodology addressed in this work consisted of mathematical analysis and modeling based on the principles of mass and energy balance, applied to a hypothetical milk pasteurization system in a continuous system.

1. The steps of the procedure followed the following sequence: **Data collection and alignment:**
The collected data include the volumetric flow rate of the fluid ($Q = 4 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$), the process inlet temperatures of the liquid ($T_i = 18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_f = 75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the specific heat of the milk ($c = 4 \text{ kJ}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$) and its density ($\rho = 1.03 \text{ kg/L}$)
2. **Unit conversion:** To enable dimensional consistency of the equations, the volumetric flow rate was converted from m^3/h to L/h . The nominal power of the available heat exchanger (30 kW) was converted to a unit of energy per minute (kJ/min)
3. **Determination of the mass flow:** Equation 5 from the theoretical framework was used ($\dot{m} = \rho \cdot Q$) to quantify the total mass of product processed per hour.
4. **Calculation of thermal demand:** Equation 6 from the theoretical framework was applied ($Q = m \cdot c \cdot \Delta T$) with the substitution of m by the mass flow (\dot{m}) to obtain the rate of heat required for pasteurization per hour
5. **Technical feasibility analysis:** The data obtained were cross-checked to generate a technical opinion between the amount of heat required by the fluid and the maximum delivery capacity of a 30kW heat exchanger over an interval of 60 minutes.

4. Results

The data were obtained through mathematical solutions and applications of data collected in the equations derived from the theoretical framework.

4.1 Calculation of the mass flow per hour

To determine the mass of fluid processed per hour, units were first converted. As it is volumetric flow rate (Q)(equation 4), $1 \text{ m}^3 = 1000 \text{ L}$, therefore:

$$Q = 4 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} = 4000 \text{ L/h} \quad (4)$$

For the mass flow we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{m} &= 1.03 \text{ kg/L} \times 4000 \text{ L/h} \\ (5) \quad \dot{m} &= 4120 \text{ kg/h} \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Calculation of the amount of heat required per hour

For the calculation of the rate of sensible heat required to raise the temperature, from 18 °C to 75 °C, the calorimetry equation (6) available in the theoretical framework was used, with the substitution of m by the mass flow $\dot{m} = 4120 \text{ kg/h}$, the result found was:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_n &= 4120 \text{ kg/h} \times [4 \text{ kJ}/(\text{kg} \cdot ^\circ\text{C})] \times (57 ^\circ\text{C}) \\ Q_n &= 939,360 \text{ kJ/h} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

A point of attention, in the calorimetry equation, is that the temperature variation can be used in Celsius or Kelvin values; as it is a variation between two temperatures, the author's use of the Celsius scale does not imply an error in the final result.

4.3 Calculation of the available energy in the heat exchanger

The heat exchanger has a nominal power of 30 kW (30 kJ/s). In minutes, the capacity is:

$$\text{Power} = 30 \text{ kJ/s} \times 60 \text{ s/min} = 1800 \text{ kJ/min} \quad (7)$$

Considering the desired operating time, 60 minutes, the total energy that the equipment can transfer is:

$$Q_p = 1800 \text{ kJ/min} \times 60 \text{ min} = 108,000 \text{ kJ} \quad (7.1)$$

4.4 Summary of the data found

Table 1 shows all the data found for analyzing the system's capacity:

Table 1- Thermal sizing of the milk pasteurization process

Variable analyzed	Value found	Unit
Mass flow (\dot{m})	4120	kg /h
Heat required (Q_n)	939,360	kJ/h
Available energy (Q_p)	108,000	kJ

Source: author (2026)

5. Data Analysis and Discussion

When analyzing the data, it is possible to point out a severe thermodynamic incompatibility between the demand of the pasteurization process and the energy power available in the model industry.

The mass balance carried out indicated that the line needs to operate with a mass flow rate of 4120 kg of milk per hour. Considering the specific heat of the fluid under study and the thermal amplitude of the adopted model, with temperatures of 18 °C at the inlet and 75 °C at the outlet, the minimum rate of heat required for the process to be carried out to ensure microbiological safety is 939,360 kJ for each hour of operation.

However, when analyzing the technical specifications of the current heat exchanger, it operates with 30 kW and this indicates that it is capable of supplying at most 108,000 kJ per operation cycle. Thus, when analyzing the difference between the energy required and the energy currently available, it is found

that the process operates with only 11.5% thermal efficiency, being, therefore, incapable of guaranteeing the demand of continuous operation.

If production continues operating with the current flow rate without changes in the power of the heat exchanger, the fluid will not reach the pasteurization temperature and the result will be a critical failure. Under food safety assurance, this product must be discarded as it poses a risk to the consumer.

For the operation to move from the inefficient thermal efficiency of 11.5% to a continuous operation that also guarantees the microbiological safety of the milk, there is a need to change the heat exchanger to one with a power of 300 kW. This change ensures the energy efficiency required for the pasteurization operation at the desired flow rate with an overload safety margin of 15%.

6. Conclusion

The present work fulfilled its objective by performing the mass and energy sizing for the unit pasteurization process of a new dairy product. The calculations based on the principles of thermodynamics showed that the 30 kW heater initially proposed is completely unfeasible for the continuous operation of 4 m³/h, since it meets a little more than one tenth of the caloric demand of the fluid.

As an engineering solution to mitigate the critical risk of under-pasteurization and to ensure both the biological integrity of the food and manufacturing efficiency, it is concluded that the ideal decision is the replacement of the current machinery with a plate heat exchanger with a nominal power of 300 kW. This modification gives the system the robustness needed to operate in steady state, aligning industrial productivity with the consumer safety requirements and the current MAPA regulations.

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